

Librarians as Digital Literacy Leaders in the Age of Generative AI and Ethical Challenges: A Study

Onwubiko Emmanuel Chidiadi

Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ikwo, Nigeria
ORCID: 0000-0001-9386-4972
onwubikoemma@yahoo.com or emmabikos@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In content creation, what is on the lips of every technology driven person is the Generative AI or generative artificial intelligence which refers to the use of AI to create new content, like text, images, music, audio, and videos. The birth of this computer propelled technology has given rise to a period of innovation which has transformed the way data is being harnessed, produced, applied, synthesized and utilized. This technology presently is permeating virtually in all human fields of endeavor including education which is the hallmark of societal development and sustainability. The irony of it is that there are two sides to this technology, the good and the ugly and librarians being facilitators of information literacy seem to be in-between the two sides to bring a balance and orderliness within the information disordered ecosystem by ensuring that users of all sort are equipped with requisite Information Literacy (IL) skills. This work therefore is an overview of Generative-AI as a concept, information literacy, digital literacy and ethics as well as Generative-AI ethical challenges and risk, librarians' role as information literacy facilitator in a Digital era and expected role of Librarians as Generative-AI literacy facilitators that will help curb ethical challenges and risk posed by Generative-AI in the global society. In all, regardless of the fact that the emergence and advancement of Generative Artificial Intelligence (Generative-AI) has created an era of innovation and like a wild wind blowing and altering the way data is being created, generated, engaged, analyzed, and used, one can deduce that there are two sides to it, the good and the ugly. Ugly side of it is that there are many risks posed by generative AI. Just like other forms of AI, it has been discovered that generative AI can affect ethical issues and risks surrounding data privacy, security, policies and workforces. Generative AI technology can also potentially introduce a series of new business risks like misinformation, plagiarism, copyright infringements and harmful content and lack of transparency among others. In some quarters, some experts believe that risks posed by generative-AI are enhanced and more concerning than those associated with other types of AI. In view of identified risk, it was suggested among others that there is need for the integration of digital ethics with digital literacy as it has significant consequences for educational settings and needs a comprehensive strategy for digital education that combines the development of skills with moral introspection in view of the fact that Librarians are essential in helping students and educators become ethically aware and technologically literate, enabling them to appropriately navigate the digital world.

Keywords: Generative-AI, Artificial Intelligence, Librarian, Information Literacy, Digital Information Literacy, Ethical challenges, Digital Ecosystem

1. INTRODUCTION

In content creation, what is on the lips of everyone is the Generative AI or generative artificial intelligence which refers to the use of AI to create new content, like text, images, music, audio, and videos. This aspect of AI is powered by foundation models (large AI models) that can multi-task and perform out-of-the-box tasks, including summarization, Question and Answer, classification, and more. Besides, with minimal training required, foundation models can be adapted for targeted use

cases with very little example data and this makes its use even by novices very popular (Cloud Google 2024). Emphatically, the emergence and advancement of Generative Artificial Intelligence (Generative-AI) has created an era of innovation, altering the way data is being created, generated, engaged, analyzed, and used. It is poised to usher in a new wave of interactive, multimodal experiences that transform how we interact with information, brands, and one another. This technology presently has permeated virtually all human fields of endeavor including education which is the hallmark of societal development and sustainability. The irony of it is that there are two sides to this technology, the good and the ugly and librarians being driving access to knowledge and facilitators of information literacy seem to be in-between the two sides to bring a balance and orderliness within the information disordered ecosystem by ensuring that users of all sort are equipped with requisite Information Literacy (IL) skills with a view to guiding users against misinformation, mal-information and disinformation that has plagued the global society as a result of the emergence of information super highway called the internet, the social media compounded by astronomical growth in information leading to information overload. With this development, the emergence of generative-Ai has raise eye-brow globally considering the ethical challenges that are associated with its application and utilization.

As revealed by Bakare-Fatungase, Adejuwon and Idowu-Davies (2024), generative-AI has created a niche in global contemporary educational discourse that it can no longer be treated with kid-glove as it is now determining the limit of teaching and learning in that teaching methodologies is being remodeled, existing educational processes being re-modified, raising students engagement and achievement a tendency that may completely change the entire global educational process. The implication is that sine generative AI makes use of sophisticated algorithms that are frequently trained on enormous datasets, it allows machines to create material autonomously that mimic the creative processes of humans thus making academic methods seamless. These technological capabilities have created a lot of enthusiasm and optimism, but it also brings up moral questions that need to be carefully thought through by stakeholders in the educational sector. Also, as these capabilities grow rapidly, an ethical challenge which is a difficult problem emerges, raising serious concerns about the appropriate application, social consequences, honourable and noble usage of these new technologies in order to guide against lack of academic integrity in the educational system. Froehlich, (2020), also allayed the same fear though they recognized the gains of AI but warned of the danger it poses against the traditional pedagogical domain and fundamental ethical challenges such as bias in training dataset that results in discriminating outputs, potential abuse for malevolent intent, and indistinct boundaries between generated and real information.

This development is a threat not only to the global educational system but particularly to librarians whose traditional duty it is to inform and educate information users on information sources and materials that are appropriate through information literacy campaigns and going by the breakthrough of information and communication technology in all aspect of our daily lives, and with contemporary skills requirement, student so to speak have come to embrace AI as a way out of every academic stress as AI now does the critical thinking for them without knowing the implications or aftermath.

With this paradigm shift, there is every need for information managers to salvage the situation by ensuring that our educators and students do not fall victim of this technological jingoism and the belief that information sourced from AI is completely factual.

In a situation like this, librarians as professionals in information management are expected to bring to bay their professional prowess and save ignorant information users from this quagmire and morass as AI-information literacy and ethical adherence facilitators and more so in this digital era. Librarians as the bridge between the information and the users should assume this rightful position and be the bridge between students, generative-AI and the teachers or lecturers as the case may be carrying users along the complexity of generative-AI domain by acting as information stewards, fact pointers, knowledge pool and encouraging latent critical thinking capabilities, ethical and netiquette considerations, stimulating generative-AI student-lecturer bond and providing a deeper comprehension of the digital world.

It is against this backdrop that this write-up becomes imperative with a view to navigating the digital information literacy horizon in relation with Generative-AI and associated ethical challenges as well as the role of librarians in making users understand these challenges that becloud Generative-AI and ways to mitigate them.

2. DEFINITION OF CONCEPTS

2.1. GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Artificial intelligence as the offshoot of information and communication technology powered by computer is making education and information handling faster and more efficient. It is breaking the paradigms of the past on how to learn and do things in effective and efficient manner. Artificial intelligence (AI), which is commonly defined as a machine's capacity to mimic intelligent human behavior, has grown from a science fiction idea to a real, widespread force that affects many facets of our everyday life. In its widest definition, AI refers to a variety of tools and systems intended to provide robots the ability to carry out operations that normally call for human intelligence (Britannica, 2024). This reveals Tech Target (2024), covers the ability to solve problems, pick up knowledge from experience, comprehend spoken language and even visualize as humans. Technological developments in machine learning, neural networks, and computing power have propelled the rise of AI, bringing in a world of previously unimaginable possibilities. AI has also been defined as the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems (apart from being astonishing in operations is a positive force for good in the world as well as an important sub discipline of computer science which was first defined during Dartmouth Conference in 1956 as a technology that can research, develop and create a "brain of machine" that is akin to that of humans and enables machines to think and learn like humans [Tech Target, 2024].

On the other hand, Generative AI or generative artificial intelligence refers to the use of AI to create new content, like text, images, music, audio, and videos. Generative AI is powered by foundation

models (large AI models) that can multi-task and perform out-of-the-box tasks, including summarization, Question and Answer, classification, and more. Plus, with minimal training required, foundation models can be adapted for targeted use cases with very little example data. Generative-AI is also perceived as a major advancement in the field of AI, especially in terms of its capacity to produce fresh, original information (Davenport & Mittal, 2022). In contrast to conventional AI models that depend on pre-established rules, generative-AI uses sophisticated algorithms to produce information materials on its own. This involves creating realistic text, graphics, and even music that can imitate the creative processes of humans. Prominent instances comprise linguistic models such as GPT-3 (Generative Pre-trained Transformer 3) and picture generators like DALL-E, which have exhibited the ability to generate extraordinarily creative and cohesive outputs [Lawton, G., 2023].

Generative-AI works using machine learning (ML) model to learn the patterns and relationships in a dataset of human-created content. It then uses the learned patterns to generate new content. The most common way to train a generative AI model is to use supervised learning - the model is given a set of human-created content and corresponding labels. It then learns to generate content that is similar to the human-created content and labeled with the same labels. Generative AI processes vast content, creating insights and answers via text, images, and user-friendly formats. Generative AI can be used to: Improve customer interactions through enhanced chat and search experiences, Explore vast amounts of unstructured data through conversational interfaces and summarizations and Assist with repetitive tasks like replying to requests for proposals (RFPs), localizing marketing content in five languages, and checking customer contracts for compliance, and more [Cloud Google 2024].

2.2. INFORMATION LITERACY

Information literacy is a set of abilities requiring individuals to 'recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate, and use effectively the needed information [9]. As expressed by UNESCO (2023), information literacy empowers people in all walks of life to seek, evaluate, use and create information effectively to achieve their personal, social, occupational and educational goals. Information-literate people are able to access information about their health, their environment, their education and work, and to make critical decisions about their lives. To this end, information literacy and lifelong learning have been described as the beacons of the information society, illuminating the courses to development, prosperity and freedom.

Coming to a digital world, information literacy requires users to have the skills to use information and communication technologies and their applications to access and create information. Closely linked to digital literacy includes computer literacy (ICT skills) and media literacy (understanding of various kinds of mediums and formats by which information is transmitted). For instance, the ability to navigate in cyberspace and negotiate hypertext multimedia documents requires both the technical skills to use the Internet and the literacy skills to interpret the information.

It was further revealed in line with the Alexandria Proclamation on Information Literacy and Lifelong Learning 2005 that for one to be truly 'information literate' it requires that the person will

simultaneously develop: awareness of how to engage with the digital world, how to find meaning in the information discovered, how to articulate what kind of information required, how to use information ethically, understand the role one can play in the communication in his or her profession **and** how to evaluate information for credibility and authority (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization 2016).

2.3. DIGITAL LITERACY AND ETHICS

To properly understand digital literacy ethics, a look at ethics as a concept is a necessity. Ethics as defined is the philosophical study of moral phenomena [Wikipedia 2024] that investigates normative questions about what people ought to do or which behavior is morally right while Encyclopedia Britannia defines it as the philosophical discipline concerned with what is morally good and bad and morally right and wrong. Its subject consists of fundamental issues of practice [Britannia (2024)]. On the part of Digital Literacy, it was initially focused on digital skills and stand-alone computers but with the emergent of the internet and social media its use has shifted some of its focus to mobile devices and to other evolving definitions of literacy that recognize the cultural and historical ways of making meaning though, digital literacy does not replace traditional methods of interpreting information but rather extends the foundational skills of these traditional literacies. Invariably, digital literacy should be considered a part of the path towards acquiring knowledge [ALA 2017].

All the same, digital literacy is seen by ALA (2017) as an individual's ability to find, evaluate, and communicate information using typing or digital media platforms. It is a combination of both technical and cognitive abilities in using information and communication technologies to create, evaluate, and share information. While UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2018) defined it as the ability to access, manage, understand, integrate, communicate, evaluate and create information safely and appropriately through digital technologies for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship. The whole idea is embedded under competences that are variously referred to as computer literacy, Information Communication Technology literacy, information literacy and media literacy. As noted by International Telecommunications Union digital literacy consists of equipping people with ICT concepts, methods and skills to enable them to use and exploit ICTs. The underlying fact noted International Telecommunication Union (2010) is that in this digital ecosystem where we live, where technology is permeating every aspect of our lives, the concept of digital ethics has become increasingly imperative. A digital ecosystem per-se is a group of interconnected information technology resources that can function as a unit. Digital ecosystems are made up of suppliers, customers, trading partners, applications, third-party data service providers and all respective technologies. Interoperability is the key to the ecosystem's success (Brush, 2024).

In this regard digital ethics is referred to as the moral principles and standards governing the ethical behavior and responsibilities of individuals, organizations, and governments in the digital realm that involves considerations of fairness, transparency, privacy, security, and technology's impact on individuals and society as a whole [Smowltech 2024]. In today's interconnected world, where digital

technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data analytics, and the internet of things are ubiquitous, digital ethics play a critical role in shaping how we interact with technology and each other. It ensures that technological advancements are aligned with ethical values and societal norms, safeguarding against potential harm and exploitation.

The correlation between digital ethics and digital literacy so to speak is that while digital ethics offers the moral foundation for responsible and conscientious interaction in the digital sphere, digital literacy provides the technological and emotional abilities to navigate around it. This implies that both serve as the most important tool for making morally sound decisions in the intricately linked world of digital technology.

3.0. GENERATIVE-AI ETHICAL CHALLENGES AND RISKS

As generative AI is getting popular and more acceptable in educational sector, institutions, businesses and organizations with these set ups working to realize the gain of the technology, they are also faced with battling of a known hydrated headed monster the ethical challenges associated with its utilization. As noted the use of generative-AI presents a number of moral issues that need to be carefully thought out thoroughly in order to guide against any iota of confusion [Humphreys, Koay, Desmond & Mealy, 2024]. To this it is imperative to explore and understand the complex ethical dilemma associated with generative-AI. Given its creative capabilities, generative-AI presents a number of complex ethical dilemmas that call into question responsible development, use and application with numbers of important things to think about such as unintentional discrimination and bias, false information and manipulation, privacy issues, absence of responsibility, unlawful use, risks to security, loss of employment, informed consent, dual-use predicament and regulatory obstacles (Humphreys, Koay, Desmond, & Mealy, 2024).

As has been noted generative AI is not different from other forms of AI that have been known to affect ethical issues and risk surrounding data privacy, security, policies and workforces adding that apart from the ethical issues and risk mentioned that are also linked with generative AI, it can also potentially introduce a series of new business risks like misinformation, plagiarism, copyright infringements and harmful content. Lack of transparency and the potential for worker displacement are additional which also need to addressed by enterprises. In fact many of the risks posed by generative AI as further revealed are pronounced and more concerning than those associated with other types of AI (Lawton, 2024). In this regard the assertion is that those risks require a comprehensive approach, including a clearly defined strategy, good governance and a commitment to responsible AI. As a result, it is advised that any corporate culture that embraces generative AI ethics must put into consideration eight important issues (Tad, 2023). These issues which are envisaged as ethical challenges and risks are: Distribution of harmful content, Copyright and legal exposure, Data privacy violations, Sensitive information disclosure, Workforce roles and morale, Data Origin, Lack of explainability and interpretability, Unintended Discrimination and Bias as well as Falsification and

Manipulation of Information, Lack of Responsibility, Unauthorized Usage and Endangered Security (Greenstein, 2022, Gupta, 2018., Johnson, 2020. Li & Chang, 2023, Ferrara, 2024, Labuz, 2023).

5.0. LIBRARIANS AS FACILITATORS OF INFORMATION LITERACY IN A DIGITAL ERA

In the dynamic journey of human technological innovation, librarians have played crucial role by being adaptable, visionary, and dedicated to making knowledge accessible despite rapidly changing technological landscapes. The librarians' journey from conventional caretakers of tangible collections to creative digital stewards affirmed Shahzad and Khan (2023). emphasized their crucial role in reshaping the information domain. This involves evolution from custodians to facilitators of digital information products and services; harnessing digital resources; information literacy advocates; integration of emerging technologies; digital access and preservation; community engagement in the digital realm; advocacy for open access and digital inclusion; as well as integrators of technology and futurists. These roles are further explained below.

5.1. NAVIGATING INFORMATION ECOSYSTEMS

When digital ethics and literacy are combined, people are better able to traverse the complex information ecosystem seamlessly. As they gain an awareness of the ethical issues surrounding online collaboration, digital communication, and information sharing, they develop into astute consumers and producers of digital content that promotes the sustainability of the human race.

5.2. EVOLUTION FROM CUSTODIANS TO FACILITATORS OF DIGITAL INFORMATION PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

The digital age has redefined the roles and responsibilities of Librarians to suite contemporary trends. These information professionals have evolved beyond their historical position as keepers of tangible collections to take on the role as facilitators of varied digital information products and services. Their ability to adjust to new technology and digital climes is demonstrated by the transition from overseeing physical collections or products to navigating enormous digital resources in different format for the provision of library and information services.

5.3. HARNESSING DIGITAL RESOURCES

Librarians welcomed the digitization of resources as well as library automation which are veritable opportunity of being able to harness digital resources in meeting clienteles' information needs without any inhibition.. They developed skills in the acquisition, processing, organizing and maintaining digital collections, making enormous repositories of human knowledge available to a global audience at the click of a button. Librarian's ability to use and navigate digital resources has become a must as the dictates of contemporary digital space requires a topnotch technologically savvy mindset and disposition in order to be relevant in meeting users' needs who are mostly netizens.

5.4. INFORMATION LITERACY ADVOCATES

Information literacy becomes increasingly important with the advent of the digital era as the space is laced with lots of intricacies and complexities which if not handled with care is gradually becoming a

bane overshadowing its positive impacts on human interactions. In this wise, Librarians have become leaders in the field of information literacy and digital user education by helping users to critically assess sources, navigate the complexity of online information, and use digital tools with responsibly and efficiency. They are becoming trainers passing down knowledge that is essential for navigating the data-rich digital environment.

5.5. INTEGRATION OF EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES

Emerging technologies are being actively incorporated into library services by librarians for the sustainability of human knowledge. Librarians have benefited from technological advancements by using online catalogs and virtual reference services like Chabots to improve user experiences and promote clientele satisfaction. In order to improve information retrieval and optimize library operations, they embraced library automation, AI, augmented reality, social media technologies, block-chain technologies, gamification, data visualization and data analytics.

5.6. DIGITAL ACCESS AND PRESERVATION

In order to protect priceless digital materials for future generations without constraints, librarians have taken on the task of digital conservation and preservation. They have created solutions to deal with data security, integrity, storage and format obsolescence, which is extending the life of digital knowledge repositories.

5.7. COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL REALM

Librarians embraced the digital sphere as part of their community participation. In order to promote information access outside of the actual library walls and to develop a feeling of community, online forums, virtual events, and digital outreach activities were essential. Librarians in the virtual world become community connectors in bring people of like minds together in discussing a societal problem in order to proffer solutions.

5.8. ADVOCACY FOR OPEN ACCESS AND DIGITAL INCLUSION

In advocating for digital inclusion and free access to knowledge, librarians play an essential role. They support programs aimed at closing the digital gap and guaranteeing that everyone in the society has fair access to digital resources and the advantages of cutting-edge technology.

5.9. INTEGRATORS OF TECHNOLOGY AND FUTURISTS

With the ability to foresee technology trends and proactively incorporate innovations into library services, librarians have developed into futurists. They worked with computer engineers, take part in the building of the digital infrastructure, and helped to shape how information will be distributed in the future.

5.10. CHALLENGES AND ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Librarians faced difficulties and moral dilemmas as technology developed, including privacy issues, digital rights, and the moral use of new technologies. Librarians have evolved into defenders of moral information practices and advocates for the proper use of technology.

6.0. LIBRARIANS AS GENERATIVE-AI LITERACY FACILITATORS: THE EXPECTATIONS

With the emergence of generative AI and its associated benefits as well as the challenging ethical issues and risks to libraries and their users, the responsibilities of libraries have become multifaceted. Librarians as prime-actors in advocacy and promotion of contemporary information related technologies it behooves them to assist users in navigating the deep waters of generative-AI literacy. It is against this backdrop that it was opined that librarians are becoming advocates or apostles of generative-AI literacy, committed to promoting comprehension, critical thinking, and responsible use of these revolutionary technologies through bridging the knowledge gap; organizing resources for generative-AI education; workshops and training programs; integration into information literacy programs; ethical considerations and responsible use; encouraging multidisciplinary education; community engagement and public discourse as well as adapting to emerging trends (Semeler, Pinto, Koltay & Rozados., 2024).

6.1. BRIDGING THE KNOWLEDGE GAP

Librarians as information managers are believed to be better placed to shorten the knowledge gap that exist in generative-AI literacy and by extension digital information literacy. It is expected that librarians should up their sleeves to determine those challenges posed by generative-AI and also educate and equip both library users and the general public with skills to navigate the trouble waters of generative-AI and other emerging information related technologies.

6.2. ORGANIZATION OF RESOURCES FOR GENERATIVE-AI EDUCATION

Librarians should ensure that all books and literary materials that enhance and promote generative-AI literacy should be selected, acquired and made accessible to users if possible there should be a bibliographic compilation of all generative-AI literacy collections for easy accessibility for all. They can also take steps further by organizing workshops, seminars and exhibitions regarding the systems and everything therein.

6.3. GENERAL TRAINING

Libraries and librarians should as a social responsibility organize at intervals workshops and regularly hold training sessions that are interactive to aid clear some uncertainty concerning generative-AI and endeavor to offer practical insights into the modus operandi of the technologies and everything they are associated with.

6.4. INTEGRATION OF GENERATIVE-AI LITERACY INTO INFORMATION LITERACY PROGRAMS

Librarians should play a pivotal role in ensuring that generative AI literacy is integrated into the wider programs of information literacy making it compulsory for all to study with emphasis on striking a balance between human generated content and that generated by generative AI, understanding bias in algorithms, and cultivating ethical considerations in the use of Generative-AI technologies.

6.5. INTERDISCIPLINARY NATURE OF TECHNOLOGICAL TRENDS

Librarians are multifaceted and ubiquitous when it comes to knowledge and information needs for this reason, they have proper understanding of the place of technological trends in every discipline and human endeavor. To this end, they support multidisciplinary initiatives in academic disciplines and work towards their successes and it is believed that generative AI will not be an exception. The expectation is that librarians should establish forums for discussion promoting a comprehensive view of generative-AI that extends beyond its technological components.

6.6. EXTENSION SERVICES

One notable work with which libraries stand out is that of community service also known as extension service. In this present dispensation posits Saeidnia (2023), librarians are expected to get involve with communities and organize meetings in which discussion on oral and societal effect of generative artificial intelligence. The community meeting should be designed in a way that experts would be called to lecture to raise the desired awareness and promote enlightened public conversation about the proper application of AI in the areas of ethical issues like accountability, privacy, and bias as well as panel discussion. The notion is that as information specialists, librarians may add to this conversation by selecting materials that address AI ethics and encourage wise choices.

6.7. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS AND RESPONSIBLE USE

As expressed by Bakare-Fatungase (2024), librarians are expected to promote proper utilization of generative-AI and ethical considerations by helping library users in resolving moral challenges involving prejudice, privacy issues, and possible abuse and by promoting a culture of responsible and contemplative interaction and by encouraging conversations about the implications of Generative-AI on society.

7.0. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Looking at the digital ecosystem and the way the world is going, one can deduce that the emergence and advancement of Generative Artificial Intelligence (Generative-AI) has created an era of innovation and like a wild wind is blowing and altering the way data is being created, generated, engaged, analyzed, and used. In the contrary, it has been discovered that there are two sides to it, the good and the ugly. Ugly side of it is that there are many risks posed by generative AI. Just like other forms of AI, it has been discovered that generative AI can affect ethical issues and risks surrounding data privacy, security, policies and workforces. Generative AI technology can also potentially introduce a series of new business risks like misinformation, plagiarism, copyright infringements and harmful content and lack of transparency among others. In some quarters, some experts believe that risks posed by generative-AI are enhanced and more concerning than those associated with other types of AI. Those risks require a comprehensive approach, including a clearly defined strategy, good governance and a commitment to responsible AI and librarians being driving access to knowledge and facilitators of information literacy seem to be in-between the two sides as to bringing a balance and orderliness within the information disordered ecosystem by ensuring that users of all sort are

equipped with requisite information literacy skills with a view to guiding users against misinformation, mal-information and disinformation that have been heightened by the emergence of generative AI and social media. Since the blurring of boundaries between created and legitimate content raises moral concerns about responsibility, transparency, and public confidence in information sources. A theoretical framework combining digital ethics and digital literacy encourages responsible use of technology, enabling people to thrive in the digital age. Librarians as information managers and facilitators of information literacy as observed from the reviews are seen to be better placed to bell the cat as it concerns equipping library users and general public with desired skills to successfully navigate this digital ecosystem. It against this backdrop, that these suggestions are put forward for application if librarians are to meet the expectations of the library users and the public.

- I. In the first instance, librarians through their various bodies should partner educators, stakeholders and curriculum planners as to smoothly incorporate digital information literacy into the curriculum, In other words, librarians should work collaboratively with all concerned entities as by working together, schemes that highlight essential digital information literacy competencies, incorporated as a compulsory course of study which will guarantee graduates that they can successfully traverse, assess, and contribute to the information ecosystem and the knowledge economy.
- II. Librarians should see it as a necessity to keep up with technological breakthroughs by constantly refreshing their knowledge through constant unlearning, relearning, acquiring more skills and more skills and being flexible in response to developing trends in generative-AI and other emerging technologies This guarantees their ability to proficiently lead the academic community through the dynamic terrain of generative-AI as the apostle for solving the ethical conundrum. Furtherance the allayed fear that the spread of Artificial Intelligence certainly brings with it a combination of exciting opportunity and change should be discarded from the minds of librarians as with forethought, planning, and consideration of the risks, librarians can ensure they are not only prepared for the transformation that AI will bring but they also are positioned to shape and then lead the world that AI is helping to create.
- III. The integration of digital ethics with digital literacy has significant consequences for educational settings. It needs a comprehensive strategy for digital education that combines the development of skills with moral introspection. Librarians are essential in helping students and educators become ethically aware and technologically literate, enabling them to appropriately navigate the digital world
- IV. To the producers of Generative-AI and the global government, the creation of thorough laws has lagged behind the generative-AI field's explosive growth. This implies that the enactment of Legal frameworks and ethical standards that are required to guarantee the proper development and use of generative-AI and other AIs are overdue. From all indication it is important to note that collaboration between researchers, developers, librarians, legislators,

and ethicists is necessary to address these ethical issues, provide rules and benchmarks for responsible generative-AI utilization..

- V. There are concerns that increased use of generative-AI just like the general AI could lead to the spread of disinformation and misinformation, not to mention security and privacy issues. Librarians can play a pivotal role in championing the responsible use of AI and must learn how to discern AI-generated text and images to pass these skills on to users.

REFERENCES

American Library Association 2016. Information literacy competency standards for higher Education, <https://alair.ala.org/items/294803b6-2521-4a96-a044-96976239e3fb>

ALA 2017. Digital Literacy: Welcome to ALA's literacy clearinghouse, <https://literacy.ala.org/digital-literacy/>

Bakare-Fatungase, O.D 2024. Staying Ahead of the Digital Curve: Librarians as Panacea of the G-AI Conundrum [PowerPoint Slides]. Institute of African Studies, Carleton University, <https://carleton.ca/qes/2024/presentation-by-dr-oluwabunmi-bakare-fatungase-at-royal-military-college-kingston/>

Bakare-Fatungase, O. D., Adejuwon, F. E. and Idowu-Davies, T. O.2024 Integrating artificial intelligence in education for sustainable development. In Using Traditional Design Methods to Enhance AI-Driven Decision Making, (pp. 231-245). IGI Global.

Britannica, 2024. Definition and Meaning of Artificial Intelligence, 2024. <https://www.britannica.com/technology/artificial-intelligence>

Britannia (2024). Ethics. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/ethics-philosophy>

Brush, K., 2024. Digital ecosystem. <https://www.techtarget.com/searchcio/definition/digital-ecosystem>

Cloud Google 2024. Use and cases of generative AI. <https://cloud.google.com/use-cases/generative-ai>

Davenport, T.H. and Mittal, N 2022. How generative AI is Changing Creative Work. *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/2022/11/how-generative-ai-is-changing-creative-work>

Ferrara, E 2024. Fairness and Bias in Artificial Intelligence: A brief survey of sources, impacts and mitigation strategies. *Sci*, 6(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/sci6010003>

Froehlich, T.J. 2020. Navigating fake news, alternative facts and misinformation in a post- truth World, USA: IGI Global DOI: 10.4018/978-1-7998-2543-2.ch003

Greenstein, B., 2022. AiThORITY Interview with Bret Greenstein, Partner, Cloud & Digital – Analytics Insights at PwC, <https://aithority.com/technology/analytics/aithority-interview-with-bret-greenstein-partner-cloud-digital-analytics-insights-at-pwc/#>

Gupta, A 2018. The Evolution of Fraud: Ethical implications in the age of large-scale data breaches and widespread artificial intelligence solutions deployment. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323857997_The_Evolution_of_Fraud_Ethical_Implications_in_the_Age_of_Large-Scale_Data_Breaches_and_Widespread_Artificial_Intelligence_Solutions_Deployment

Humphreys, D., Koay, A., Desmond, D., and Mealy, E 2024. AI hype as a cyber security risk: The moral responsibility of implementing Generative AI in business, *AI Ethics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-024-00443-4>. (Accessed June 21, 2024)

International Telecommunication Union (2010). World Telecommunication/ICT Development Report: Monitoring the WSIS Targets <https://unevoc.unesco.org/home/TVETipedia+Glossary/show=term/term=Digital+literacy>

Johnson, B 2020. Automation and its implications for social inequality. *Journal of Technology and Society*, 22(2), 59-63.

Labuz, M. 2023. Regulating deep fakes in the artificial intelligence act. *Applied Cyber and Internet Governance*. <https://www.acigjournal.com/Regulating-Deep-Fakes-in-the-ArtificialIntelligence-Act,184302,0,2.html>.

Lawton, G., 2023. What is Generative AI? Everything you need to know. Tech Accelerator. <https://www.techtarget.com/searchenterpriseai/definition/generative-AI>

Lawton, G.2024. Generative AI ethics: 8 biggest concerns and risks. <https://www.techtarget.com/searchenterpriseai/tip/Generative-AI-ethics-8-biggest-concerns>

Li, J.,and Chang, X 2023. Combating misinformation by sharing the truth: A study on the spread of fact-checks on social media. *Information System Front.* 25, 1479–1493. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-022-10296-z>

Nah, F. F.-H., Zheng, R., Cai, J., Siau, K.,and Chen, L 2023. Generative AI and ChatGPT:Applications, Challenges, and AI-Human Collaboration. *Journal of Information Technology Case and Application Research*, 25(3), 277-304. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15228053.2023.2233814>

Saeidnia, H.R. 2023. Ethical artificial intelligence (AI): Confronting bias and discrimination in the library and information industry. *Library Hi Tech News*. DOI: 10.1108/LHTN-10-2023-0182

Semeler, A.R., Pinto, A.L., Koltay, T., and Rozados, H., 2024. Algorithmic literacy: Generative artificial intelligence technologies for data librarians. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/377336874_ALGORITHMIC_LITERACY_Generative_Artificial_Intelligence_Technologies_for_Data_Librarians/citations

Shahzad, K., and Khan, S.A 2023. Effects of e-learning technologies on university librarians and Libraries: A systematic literature review. *The Electronic Library*. 41(4), 528 - 554. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EL-04-2023-0076>

Smowltech 2024. Digital ethics: definition and examples. <https://smowl.net/en/blog/digital-ethics/>

Tad, N 2023. How to Put Generative AI to work responsibly, <https://www.bcg.com/publications/2023/responsible-ai-crucial-to-avoid-new-ai-tech-risks>

Tech Target, 2024. How does AI works? <http://www.techtarget.com/serachenterpriseai/definition/ai>

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization 2006. Alexandria Proclamation on Information Literacy and Lifelong Learning, <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000144820>

UNESCO 2023. Information literacy, <https://www.unesco.org/en/ifap/information-literacy>

UNESCO Institute for Statistics 2018. A global framework of reference on digital literacy skills for Indicator 4.4.2., <https://unevoc.unesco.org/home/TVETipedia+Glossary/show=term/term=Digital+literacy>

Wikipedia 2024. Ethics, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ethics>